

chamber. In this note we report such facile oxidation of alcohol held in the cathode chamber presumably caused by the above mechanism.

Experimental

The apparatus was an ordinary U-tube (20 cm $\times$ 18 mm o.d.) with a fine fritted glass partition at the bottom (the size not critical). The electrodes were bright platinum foils (1 cm $\times$ 1 cm). The cathode side was fitted with a cork through which passed a long vertical tube to take care of the electro-osmotic rise. The catholyte is a 1% solution of ethyl alcohol whereas the anolyte is distilled water. 230 V from D.C. mains are directly applied. Water being highly non-conducting only a few hundred microamperes passed at the beginning. A higher D.C. voltage may be applied if available. The current slowly rose to about 1 mA and somewhat beyond. Due to the high electro-osmotic rise of distilled water at the cathode side, 0.01 N Na_2SO_4 or 0.01 N H_2SO_4 solution was better used instead. About 1-4 mA current was passed for 24 h. Few experiments were also done in a simple U-tube (30 cm $\times$ 32 mm o.d.) as used in our previous experiments for the study of non-Faradaic electrolysis⁸. In such U-tube the required amount of alcohol was added very carefully from the cathode side just after the electrolysis started. Electro-osmosis did not take place due to the absence of fritted glass partition at the bottom. Therefore, the experiment was done even with distilled water. But due to very low current density, acid conversion was less than that with 0.01 N or 0.001 N H_2SO_4 solution.

What happens is that H_3O^+ enters the cathode chamber and oxidises the alcohol to acetic acid. The acetic acid as it forms migrates to the anode chamber and so almost the whole product of oxidation formed inside the cathode chamber collects in the anolyte. The amount of acetic acid formed is found by titration with 0.1 N NaOH using phenolphthalein as indicator. Since 4 F are theoretically needed to convert 1 mole alcohol to 1 mole acetic acid ($\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH} + 2\text{O} = \text{CH}_3\text{COOH} + \text{H}_2\text{O}$) and since 1 mA per day is approximately equal to 1 meqv., it is easily seen that if the efficiency is cent per cent, 10 ml 0.1 N alkali would be the titre in 4 days at current strength of 1 mA. The actual efficiency is found to be about 70 to 90 per cent, a remarkable yield.

It may be thought that alcohol is diffusing to the anode chamber and getting oxidised there. The contrary is proved by the fact that in a control experiment no detectable amount of alcohol (acid $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ test) is found in the anode chamber consistent with the extremely slow rate of diffusion through such fine 'frit'. Even a N $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ solution shows no detectable diffusion in a week. Furthermore, electro-osmotic flow takes place in the reverse direction towards the cathode. A portion (5 to 10%) of acetic acid formed is also found in the cathode chamber itself.

Not only ethyl alcohol, but many other substances are reacted upon in the same way. For example, methyl alcohol is oxidised to formic acid and carbon dioxide, other alcohols to the corresponding acids, urea to ammonia and so on which will be reported in a separate publication. We record here only the remarkable fact that oxidation may take place even in the catholyte with high current efficiency but low power efficiency. Efforts are being made to remove the latter hurdle in order to make the process attractive and cost-efficient.

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Ultraviolet and Visible Spectral Studies of Anthraquinonyl and Other Hydroxytriazenes

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HYDROXYTRIAZENES, also called diazohydroxyamino compounds and triazen oxides¹ have been established as an important group of chelating agents^{2,3}. There is a growing interest⁴⁻⁷ in these compounds. In this communication the ultraviolet and visible spectral studies of nine hydroxytriazenes have been reported.

Experimental

The ultraviolet and visible absorption spectra were taken in absolute alcohol on a Beckmann DB spectrophotometer using quartz and glass cells of 1.0 cm pathlength. The results obtained (λ_{max} , $\log \epsilon$) are given in Table 1.

From Table 1 it is not possible to make any exact correlation with the structure. Still the following points are noteworthy.

(a) Compounds no. 1, 2 and 3 show two absorption maxima. The first one appears at 418-420 nm which may be assigned to $n-\pi^*$ transition. The second one appears in the range 300-388 nm and specifically at 347 ± 5 nm in compounds no. 1, 2 and 3. It seems to be due to the conjugation between $-\text{N}=\text{N}-$ and the aryl nucleus and may be designated as $\pi-\pi^*$ transition.

TABLE 1

Sl. no.	R-N-OH		R-N-O	
	R	R'	EtOH (nm)	Triazen oxide (II) log ϵ
1.	OH ₂	2'-anthraquinonyl	342 420	4.318 4.029
2.	O ₂ H ₆	2'-anthraquinonyl	342 418	4.107 3.798
3.	O ₆ H ₄	2'-anthraquinonyl	352 420	4.438 4.207
4.	O ₆ H ₄	o-carboxyphenyl	218 242 266	4.401 4.365 4.531
5.	OH ₂	o-nitrophenyl	204-210 256-264 284-292	3.886 4.200 4.200
6.	OH ₂	p-nitrophenyl	214 242 276 284	3.861 3.209 3.079 3.792
7.	n-C ₆ H ₅	phenyl	222-223 291 810-812	3.997 4.162 4.189
8.	n-C ₆ H ₄	p-tolyl	222 292 810-812	4.189 4.162 3.977
9.	N-1,1'-(2,2'-Dimethyl-4,4'-biphenyleno)-bis(3-N-hydroxy-3-ethyltriazene)		218 242 368	4.401 4.365 4.581

(b) In compounds no. 5 to 8 an absorption maximum appears in the range 276-292 nm, which may be taken to indicate that there is a greater contribution of the triazene oxide form (II) in these compounds. Disappearance of this band in compounds no. 1 to 4 and 9 is difficult to explain but it seems that a lesser contribution of the hydroxy-triazene form (I) may be responsible for this phenomenon.

(c) In compounds no. 4 to 9 there appears a band in the range 214 to 228 nm and an additional band at 253 ± 11 nm in compounds no. 4, 5, 6 and 9, which may be correlated to the π - π^* band of benzene displaced to the longer wavelengths due to substitution on the benzene ring.

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Preparation and Antibacterial Activities of 2-Aryl-3-[α -(2-hydroxy-1-naphthyl)benzyl]-4-thiazolidinones

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THIAZOLIDINONES, the derivatives of thiazolidine having a carbonyl group at 2, 4 or 5 position, have been studied in detail recently¹⁻³. Several reviews have been written on thiazolidinones which highlight their chemistry and implications⁴⁻¹². The present investigation has been undertaken to compare the effect of azomethines (II) and thiazolidinones (III) on antimycobacterial and antibacterial activity. The 2-aryl-3-[α -(2-hydroxy-1-naphthyl)benzyl]-4-thiazolidinones (III) have been prepared by the reaction of mercaptoacetic acid with azomethines (II) and tested against *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (H₃₇R_V), *E. coli* and *S. aureus*.

The structure of the title compound (III) has been elucidated on the basis of their elemental analysis, ir and uv spectra. The Schiff bases (II) gave strong band in the region 1630-1615 cm⁻¹, which disappeared by thiazolidine ring formation. The compound III showed $\lambda_{\max}$ at 235, 342 nm and $\nu_{\max}$ at 1630 and 1655 cm⁻¹. The ir spectra were recorded on Beckman IR 20 spectrophotometer.

Experimental

α -(2-Hydroxy-1-naphthyl)-benzylamine (I) has been prepared following the method described in the literature^{1,4,13}.

Azomethines (II): The appropriate aldehyde (0.01 mol) and I (0.01 mol) were dissolved in EtOH (95%, 50 ml) and the solution refluxed for 3 h, the excess solvent distilled until the Schiff base commenced to crystallise (Table 1 and 3).

4-Thiazolidinones (III): The mixture of appropriate azomethine (II, 0.01 mol) and thioglycolic acid (0.01 mol) in anhydrous benzene (30 ml) was refluxed for 8 h and the excess solvent and thioglycolic acid removed under vacuum. The residue was washed thoroughly with aqueous NaHCO₃ and water, dried and crystallised from ethanol (95%) (Table 2 and 3).

Pharmacological screening: The *in vitro* anti-tubercular activity of the compounds I, II and III was studied against H₃₇R_V strain of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* in Lowenstein-Jensen egg media at 0.02 mg/ml. The retardation of the growth rate has been studied upto 6 weeks at 37°.

The antibacterial activities of the compounds I, II and III were tested by N-agar pour-plate